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TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF FORMING SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract

This article was written in order to determine the cause of the problem of the formation of a certain competence of students in the English lesson in accordance with the changes made to the education system of Kazakhstan. The question included in the article is aimed at the formation of the current socio-cultural competence of schoolchildren through foreign language lessons. And do all teachers fulfill this requirement, or do they accept sociocultural competence as a necessary and important skill? According to the results of the survey conducted during the writing of the article, it was determined and analyzed how teachers of different levels take responsibility for this competence.

Keywords: *competence, sociocultural competence, formation of sociocultural competence, teachers' perception, English classes*

Introduction

The intense political, social and economic transformations in the society of Kazakhstan under the influence of global development led to radical changes in the education system. The directions in the education system are determined according to the requirements of modern society [1]. In addition, the goals and objectives of education in the education system are constantly updated in the strategic plan of each period. One of them is to educate competent and qualified generation starting from the school walls so that the citizens of the state can become competitive individuals [2].

According to the state program of education and science development of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2020-2025, combining the socio-economic development of the country with science, the main goal is to increase the literacy level of citizens by eliminating regional differences, to learn foreign languages in depth, and to form the competencies inherent in a highly intelligent person [3]. Supplementing the aforementioned legislative program with such directions was directly related to the progress of the modern innovative and integrated borderless society.

The modern education system requires the development of critical thinking ability of a person, the ability to analyze it and express one's point of view in the era of large-scale information flow, as well as to have communication skills. Based on this, a person can overcome any misunderstandings and difficulties through cultural experience in the process of establishing a relationship with a representative of another culture. Cultural awareness and communication skills ensure successful interpersonal dialogue [4]. As a rule, learning and mastering the differences between cultures takes place in foreign language classes. Based on this, it can

be said that sociocultural competence is a component that plays a major role in human development.

That is, the importance of formation of sociocultural competence was directly related to the growing trend of learning any foreign language and the intermingling of different world cultures. The presence of sociocultural competence in a person and the components that are the basis for its formation have been intensively studied in recent decades. In addition to foreign researchers, this article will discuss the work of scientists who studied this competence in coordination with the needs of the education system of Kazakhstan.

Literature review

During the analysis of social and cultural competence on a theoretical and methodological basis, it is necessary to consider the origin of this competence. The American linguist N. Chomsky reintroduced the concept of competence in teaching a foreign language into the circulation of science [5]. In his studying, the concept of competence is described as consisting of a set of abilities aimed at the implementation of linguistic activity.

Over time, the content of the concept of competence increased, and the components or sub-competencies that are part of it began to be studied individually. Among them, its communicative competence within the framework of language competence was mentioned for the first time in the work of the American sociolinguist D. Hymes [6]. According to his description, cognitive and social factors interact in knowing and using a foreign language within the framework of communicative competence.

It has become known that this communicative competence, which has not lost its relevance, but is considered the main prerequisite for learning a foreign language, cannot guarantee the success of intercultural

mutual dialogue [1]. Here, in teaching a foreign language, there is a problem of teaching communication, taking into account the social factors and cultural features of that language.

In teaching a foreign language, Safonova [7], Sysoev [8], Galskova [9], Elizarova [10] considered the sociocultural concept as a component of communicative competence and formulated its content using its main components. Safonova [7] says that for the formation of sociocultural competence in an individual, it is necessary to learn different civilizations and norms of communication, some special facts, while developing his personal qualities, knowledge and skills, to rely on these guidelines in intercultural communication.

In addition, according to the research of Sysoev [11], the content of socio-cultural competence consists of a set of national and spiritual values, national mentality, communication and traditional features of the language culture being learned.

According to Efremova [12], sociocultural competence of students consists of the sum of their knowledge about their own culture and the culture of the language they are learning, and it is considered as one component of communicative competence. On this basis, communicating skills are formed in the student depending on the relationship situation, and he is taught to adapt his behavior depending on the environment.

Furthermore, in the research of Kunanbayeva [13], who contributed to the development of domestic science, sociocultural competence is a prerequisite for understanding between two cultures when establishing a relationship with a representative of another culture. Therefore, mastering a foreign language only as a means of communication cannot be the key to successful communication [13]. In this regard, in the process of teaching a foreign language, teaching the semantic content of that country's culture was given the main attention. Because the greater the difference between languages and cultures, the more difficult it is to communicate and establish a dialogue with representatives of those languages.

Then it can be summarized that sociocultural competence is a person's knowledge in the social and cultural sphere and the ability to establish relations with other cultures, the ability to use the integrative process correctly.

The importance of sociocultural competence in the society of Kazakhstan is caused by raising the level of domestic education to a new innovative level, based on international education models, within the framework of the country's transition to a trilingual education system [14].

The importance of this problem is not only in Kazakhstan, in fact, in many educational systems of the world, the development of students' ability to establish intercultural relations, teaching to maintain tolerance, or the formation of general personality traits have not yet been fully addressed [12]. Therefore, here the teacher's role in the development of sociocultural competence prevails.

For many years in Kazakhstan, foreign language educational materials and curricula have been prepared in accordance with the content of general education. At

that moment, it was necessary to prepare educational requirements and tasks according to competence-based context. In particular, in accordance with the requirements of the Law on Education, it was required to create a sociocultural component in foreign language materials in order to train future teachers, compile textbooks, and to form competence in teaching students [15].

In addition, many foreign language specialists of Kazakhstan did not fully understand the importance and meaning of this competence. For that reason, they did not create a specific plan for the formation of sociocultural competence. As a result, the formation of this competence in the educational system was developing differently in all educational institutions.

Another reason for such disparity is that teachers' lack of special professional knowledge or sociocultural experience aimed at competence has a negative impact on the educational process. In this regard, in recent years, the criteria determining the formation and development of sociocultural competence in a foreign language teacher [16] have been studied and conducted a special examination with the research of pedagogic and methodical specialists of Kazakhstan. In their study, the social and cultural competence of a foreign language teacher consists of an integrated complex of knowledge that forms their social and cultural knowledge and skills, abilities, and personal qualities. Based on these characteristics, the authors [16] divided the criteria for the formation of sociocultural competence into the following groups: cognitive (the culture, traditions, geography, history of the language being studied, the sociocultural content of words, the behavior of representatives of that language norms, etc.), operational and technological (skills to search, analyze and use social and cultural information), personal (showing tolerance and empathy for another culture, learning its peculiarities, etc.).

Foreign language teachers with the above-mentioned criteria can assess their students' sociocultural competence at a special level to determine whether it has been formed and developed [17].

Although the directions of the foreign language learning process are gradually changing towards the formation of sociocultural competence, there are still teachers who do not include this competence in the curriculum. Its reasons can be different in addition to the factors mentioned above. Therefore, the relevance of this article lies here. In order to determine the causes of this problem, the following research questions are asked:

1 What are the teachers' perceptions of forming sociocultural competence in secondary school students?

2 Do teachers include sociocultural competence as an important skill in the teaching process?

3 What kind of tools and approaches do teachers use to form sociocultural competence of students?

Methods

1 Research design

This research paper was carried out at Kazakh Ablai Khan University of International Relations and

World Languages at the Department of Foreign language education Methodology. The data were collected through a questionnaire, which analyzed and determined the level of understanding and application of sociocultural competence of foreign language teachers teaching in secondary schools. The study of the factors influencing the perception of English language teachers, using questionnaire questions, revealed the main key feature that affects the formation of the sociocultural competence of their students.

2 Participants

This study involved 21 teachers working in various types of schools in Almaty. The teachers who participated in the survey varied in age, university education, work experience, as well as the teaching requirements and teaching materials of the school where they work, and the classroom environment and the number of students in their class. In this regard, when formulating the survey questions, various aspects of determining their professional knowledge and sociocultural competence were taken into account.

Table 1

Gender	Degree	Experience	School	Class
Female – 19 (90,5%)	Undergraduate – 4 (19%)	1-1,5 years – 5	Private school – 4 (19%)	5-7 th grades – 8 (38,1%)
Male – 2 (9,5%)	Associate degree – 1 (4,8%)	2-4 years – 13	State school – 8 (38,1%)	8-9 th grades – 5 (23,8%)
Prefer not to say – 0	Master's – 15 (71,4%)	5-9 years – 3	Language school – 8 (38,1%)	Only primary school – 6 (28,6%)
	Doctorate – 1 (4,8%)	10 and more – 0	Private tutor – 1 (4,8%)	Only high school – 2 (9,5%)

As it is illustrated in table 1, most of the teachers' gender is female and most of the respondents have master's degrees. More than half of the participants have 2-4 years of work experience, which means that many of them have already been aware of new requirements of the education system, where they must be acquainted with competence-based learning.

3 Instruments

The researcher formulated survey questions in English, in which answers were received in English, and. The survey was conducted in the form of a Likert scale of 5 response options: from strongly disagree to strongly agree. In addition to answering questions based on close-ended questions, the questionnaire method used multiple-choice questions, as well as open-ended questions was utilized in order to gather a more detailed answer from the participants' point of view. During the analysis of the answers to the questionnaire, the degree and work experience of teachers in different categories were taken into account. In addition, the survey was piloted to preserve the anonymity of the teachers and to ensure reliability and validity.

4 Research procedure

Before conducting the research, the author of the article reviewed the relevant literature revealing the relevance of the topic, and based on the previous research works, she designed a questionnaire according to the relevance of the article and checked the reliability of the research tool. Taking into account the requirements, after ensuring the originality of the work, the survey questions were conducted online in the Google Form

format. Names, jobs and degrees of teachers participating in the survey were kept confidential. After the survey responses were collected, the data was analyzed. On the basis of that, the study of the main factors that influenced the different perception of sociocultural competence and its use by English language teachers was discussed.

Results

This research work conducted a questionnaire about teachers' awareness and attitude towards implementing sociocultural competence in English classrooms. The responses were analyzed by the author of this academic paper, and it helped the researcher to have an overview of teachers' perception and understanding of sociocultural competence, particularly, their attitude in the formation of sociocultural competence among secondary school students in English language classrooms.

Research question 1

The research question 1 was formed to identify teachers' perceptions of forming sociocultural competence in secondary school students. As Figure 1 shows, the majority of the respondents (57,1%) agree with the statements that according to the requirements of the Education system of Kazakhstan, the English language curriculum should be created on the basis of a competency-based approach. This implies the teachers' positive perception of forming a competence. In addition, according to the results, 14,3% of teachers strongly agree with the competence-based approach in teaching. Only a few of them showed their negative attitude, while 5 of the participants kept neutrality.

1. According to the requirements of the Education system of Kazakhstan, the English language curriculum should be created on the basis of a competency-based approach?

21 responses

Figure 1. According to the requirements of the Education system of Kazakhstan, the English language curriculum should be created on the basis of a competency-based approach

As it is indicated in Table 2, the teachers' attitude towards sociocultural competence was analyzed in order to reveal participants' clear picture about the essence of this competence and suitable environment for its forming.

Table 2

Teachers' attitude towards sociocultural competence

№	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Due to the integration of world cultures and languages in the modern world, sociocultural competence has become one of the most important competences that must be formed in a person?	0	1 (4,8%)	4 (19%)	12(57,1%)	4 (19%)
The English class is the only environment in which a person's sociocultural competence is developed because learning English allows us to become familiar with the cultures of the English-speaking community.	0	3(14,3%)	6(28,6%)	38(38,1%)	4 (19%)

Both Figure 1 and Table 2 demonstrates the positive attitude of English language educators towards the use of sociocultural competence in practice.

Research question 2

The aim of the research question 2 was to discover teachers' readiness to include sociocultural competence

as an important skill in the teaching process of foreign language (Figure 2). Based on the responses for this question, if teachers incorporate sociocultural in their classroom, what skills do they develop in their students?

4. If you know the importance of sociocultural competence, do you include it in your lesson plan to develop it in your students?

21 responses

Figure 2. If you know the importance of sociocultural competence, do you include it in your lesson plan to develop it in your students?

5. If you incorporate sociocultural competence into your practice, what skills will it develop in your students?

21 responses

Figure 3. If you incorporate sociocultural competence into your practice, what skills will it develop in your students?

6. If you have not implemented sociocultural competence in your classroom yet or if you have difficulties in applying it, then what is the reason?

21 responses

Figure 4. If you have not implemented sociocultural competence in your classroom yet or if you have difficulties in applying it, then what is the reason?

Figure 3 provides us with the information about the skills of students which will be formed with the help of sociocultural competence in the English language classroom. 42,9% of respondents teach their students to become an intermediary of intercultural communication. Only 2 people think that to get acquainted with the linguistic picture of the world and acceptable speech practices are main skills. Other participants think that achieving intercultural mutual understanding and being aware of differences in appearance, behavior and cultural identity are significant skills that students should develop. Moreover, figure 4 shows the obstacles in implementing sociocultural competence in the English language classroom. Majority of teachers think that

lack of tools in the classroom does not let them fully implement this competence, while others think that students' English language level does not allow them to apply sociocultural competence.

Research question 3

The aim of the 3rd research question was to identify the most effective tools or techniques to develop sociocultural competence in the English language classroom. As Figure 5 demonstrates, many respondents chose gamification, role-playing or theatrical games, because of their interaction and communication-based approach. More efficient types of tool for second groups of teachers are multimedia, ICT technologies, audio-visual tools.

7. Which of the technologies listed below, in your opinion, will be more effective for the development of sociocultural competence of secondary school students?

21 responses

Figure 5. Which of the technologies listed below, in your opinion, will be more effective for the development of sociocultural competence of students?

Discussion

The primary purpose of this research was to study the teachers' perception of sociocultural competence in English classes in secondary schools. Prior studies showed that despite the existence of a professional knowledge base of teachers, in practice, their failure to consider the relevance of sociocultural competence and the importance of including it in the class plan as one of the problems that must be solved in the current education system hinders the development of students' communication [15].

However, the fact that teachers, discovering the meaning and importance of sociocultural competence, begin to consider this competence as one of the skills that should be found in a modern person, shows that their attitude towards this competence is positive. As stated in the literature review, when English language teachers possess all of the three criteria of sociocultural competence characteristics [16], they can understand the significance of this competence and can apply it in their classroom. As in the current modern education system, the requirements for the curriculum in foreign language classes of all schools are the same [18], then the findings of this research reinforced this study conducted by Kim and Amirova [16], where English language teachers' implement sociocultural competence into their secondary school classes, as well as they apply specific modes of techniques in order to develop this competence on students. Therefore, based on Figure 4, the results of the research show that more than half of the teachers, who participated in the questionnaire, use this competence only in certain classes. However, there still exist common issues on implementing sociocultural competence properly. As indicated before, lack of tools in the classroom and students' English language level interferes with the lesson. Since most of the respondents here are young professionals and the finding of the research cannot be a common statistic for all Kazakhstani schools.

Another reason for implementing sociocultural competence is that this competence allows learners to

adapt in various kinds of cultures and those communicative norms of interaction, phenomena and cultural identity [19]. Apparently, there is a need for young English language educators with advanced thinking capable and sociocultural condition of professional activity [20], who teach and direct their students to develop this competence using approaches and techniques. The findings suggested that activity-based techniques are more effective tools to apply sociocultural competence; a significant number of secondary school teachers utilize gamification, role-playing and theatrical games in their classroom. Since other tools such as multimedia or ICT technologies, literary texts or songs are less important, which may explain the non-interactive method used in the formation of sociocultural competence of secondary school students. It can therefore be assumed that the teachers' awareness of sociocultural competence and its significance leads them to establish a sociocultural competence-based environment in the classroom is useful for maintaining secondary school students' positive attitudes, which will affect the improvement of their competence.

Conclusion

The findings reveal teachers' perception of forming sociocultural competence among secondary school students in English classes. Analysis of theoretical sources set up sociocultural competence as one of the significant competences of the modern world, which led a person to own necessary skills and qualities that will be useful in the communication with other cultures. This study points out both teachers' positive and negative outlook on utilizing sociocultural competence for secondary school students in English classrooms. This shows that developing sociocultural competence of students in the English language will establish a certain intercultural understanding.

This research work found out that regardless of having various professional backgrounds, teachers could not equally apply sociocultural competence in all classes, because of some reasons. It is mainly due to the classroom environment and students' English language

level. In addition, analysis of survey questions lets researcher identify the tools and techniques that will be used to apply sociocultural competence. However, due to the time limitation, the survey covered only a small number of teachers, which can not reveal the attitude and perceptions of all educators towards sociocultural competence in Kazakhstan. The recommendations for further research would be: a) to identify the most effective tool for forming sociocultural competence of secondary school children; on this basis b) to conduct an experiment to verify the usefulness of this technology in forming sociocultural competence of students.

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